

Synthesis and Spectral Studies of Triphenylantimony(V) Oximates and Benzamidoximate

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Complexes of the general formula, $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb}(\text{ONCRR}')_2$, (where R and R' = Me, Me; Me, Et; Me, Pr; Me, Ph; Et, Et; Et, Pr and NH_2 , Ph), have been synthesised and characterised. A trigonal bipyramidal geometry has been suggested for these complexes. They can be purified by recrystallization and on distillation under reduced pressure, they yield triphenylantimony.

THERE has been a considerable interest in the chemistry of organoantimony(V) complexes in recent years¹⁻³. Significant changes in bonding and stereochemistry have been observed in a number of organoantimony derivatives on increasing the alkyl or aryl component on antimony atom⁴⁻⁷. Except a preliminary report⁸ on triphenylantimony(V) diacetaldoximate, no study appears to have been made on antimony(V) oximates. In this communication, we report the synthesis and spectroscopic studies of oximates and benzamidoximate of triphenylantimony(V).

Experimental

Special precautions were taken to exclude moisture. Benzene and isopropanol were dried by usual method. $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb}(\text{OMe})_2$ was prepared by the reaction of triphenylantimony dichloride with sodium methoxide in methanol⁴. Oximes were prepared using standard techniques and were purified by careful fractionation⁹.

Molecular weight, were determined cryoscopically in freezing benzene. IR spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer in the range of $4000-200\text{ cm}^{-1}$ using CsI optics. PMR spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer R12B spectrometer working at 60MHz, in CDCl_3 solutions using TMS as an external standard.

Reaction between Ph_3SbCl_2 and Sodium Salt of Methyl Ethyl Ketoxime in 1 : 2 Molar Ratio :

Triphenylantimony dichloride (2.90 g) was added to the suspension of the sodium salt of methyl ethyl ketoxime (prepared from 0.33 g sodium and 1.20 g ligand) in benzene. Reactants were refluxed for about two hours. Sodium chloride was filtered off. Filtrate was evaporated under vacuum giving white solid product. The compound was

recrystallized by dissolving in ~3 ml benzene and keeping the whole solution in the freezer for a night after adding ~25 ml light petroleum. Crystals so obtained were dried under vacuum. Yield ~35% and M.P. 65-66°. Anal. Found : C, 60.12; H, 6.29; N, 5.40; Sb, 23.64%. $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb}(\text{ONCMeEt})_2$. Calcd. : C, 59.45; H, 5.95; N, 5.33; Sb, 23.18%.

Other complexes were prepared in a similar manner and are summarized in Table 1.

Distillation of $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb}(\text{ONCMe}_2)_2$:

$\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb}(\text{ONCMe}_2)_2$ (2.88 g) was heated at 0.4 mm pressure. At about 180° bath temperature a yellow crystalline product (0.17 g) b.p. 50-55° was collected. On increasing the bath temperature (180-230°) another fraction (1.36 g) was obtained, b.p. 165-66°. The latter compound, a viscous liquid, was further purified by redistillation in quantitative yield. This product was solidified by adding a crystal of triphenylantimony. Anal. of low boiling component (50-55°/0.4 mm) Found : N, 18.13% m.p. 58-60°. Me_2CNOH . Calcd. : N, 19.18%, m.p. 59°. Anal. of high boiling component (165-66°/0.4 mm) Found : C, 61.83; H, 4.34; Sb, 34.14%. Ph_3Sb . Calcd. : C, 61.23; H, 4.28; Sb, 34.49%.

Results and Discussion

Triphenylantimony(V) diketomixates of the type, $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb}(\text{ONCRR}')_2$, may be prepared from the following reactions :

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TABLE I—REACTIONS OF TRIPHENYLANTIMONYDICHLORIDE WITH SODIUM SALT OF OXIMES

R' R R & R' =	Reactants (g)		Product and % yield of Recrystallized Product	M.P. (°C)	% Analysis Found (calc)				IR Assignments** νC=N cm ⁻¹	% Yield of Triphenylantimony on Distillation (B.P.°C/mm)
	Sodium Metal	Ph ₃ SbCl ₂			C	H	Sb	N		
Me, Me 0.85	0.27	2.45	Ph ₃ Sb(ONCMe ₂) ₂ ~78	116	55.54	4.74	24.81	5.88	1645m	~53
					(57.97)	(5.47)	(24.52)	(5.63)	1615m	(165-66/0.4)
Et, Me 1.20	0.33	2.90	Ph ₃ Sb(ONCMeEt) ₂ ~35	65-66	60.12	6.29	23.64	5.40	1620w	~39
					(59.45)	(5.95)	(23.18)	(5.33)		(173/1.0)
Me, Pr 1.44	0.34	3.00	Ph ₃ Sb(ONCMePr) ₂ ~18	81-82	59.47	6.47	22.34	5.02	1605w	~49
					(60.77)	(6.38)	(22.00)	(5.06)		(155-56/0.05)
Me, Ph 1.59	0.28	2.49	Ph ₃ Sb(ONCMePh) ₂ ~38	150-54	65.11	4.81	20.27	4.25	1580m	~12
					(65.72)	(5.03)	(19.60)	(4.51)		(160-54/0.4)
Et, Et 1.34	0.31	2.80	Ph ₃ Sb(ONCEt ₂) ₂ ~50	64	60.01	6.85	22.39	4.90	1645vw	~41
					(60.77)	(6.38)	(22.00)	(5.06)	1615vw	(162-64/0.3)
Et, Pr 1.50	0.31	2.77	Ph ₃ Sb(ONCEtPr) ₂ ~54	90-91	61.43	7.29	22.70	4.77	1602w	~38
					(61.98)	(6.76)	(20.94)	(4.82)		(165-/0.3)
Ph NH ₂	1.71	2.61	Ph ₃ Sb(ONCNH ₂ Ph) ₂ ~93	143-4	60.98	4.23	18.39	8.55	1605s	~16
					(61.65)	(4.69)	(19.53)	(8.99)		(160/1.0)

** Where s=strong, m=medium, w=weak and vw=very weak.

(where R and R' = Me, Me ; Me, Et ; Me, Pr ; Me, Ph ; Et, Et ; Et, Pr and NH₂, Ph).

All these compounds are white crystalline solids and can be recrystallized from benzene light petroleum mixture. They are hydrolytically unstable and are soluble in common organic solvents. Cryoscopic molecular weight determinations of some of these complexes indicate that they are monomeric in benzene.

A weak broad band in the region 3000-3380 cm⁻¹, which has been assigned to the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded OH in free oximes¹⁰, is absent in the IR spectra of these complexes. Compared to νC=N vibration at ~1668 cm⁻¹ in the free oximes, two νC=N vibrations at ~1640 cm⁻¹ and 1615 cm⁻¹ have been observed in the complexes of the type Ph₃Sb(ONCRR')₂ (where R=R'=Me or Et). In cases, where R≠R', only one C=N stretching vibration has been observed in the region 1620-1580 cm⁻¹. A lowering of about 30-40 cm⁻¹ may be ascribed to the stabilization of C=N bond by resonance¹¹ with non-bonding electron pair on oxygen atom of the imino group. Removal of hydrogen by more electropositive antimony may

favour the structure $\begin{array}{c} \text{R} \\ \diagdown \\ \text{C} \rightarrow \text{N} = \overset{+}{\text{O}} \\ \diagup \\ \text{R}' \end{array}$ which should

result in a decrease of C=N frequency due to partial attainment of single bond character^{12,13}. Alternatively, this type of lowering may also be ascribed to the mass effect¹⁴.

Two bands at 3460 and 3360 cm⁻¹ in Ph₃Sb(ONCNH₂Ph) have been assigned for free amino group. A down-field shift in C=N stretching by ~35 cm⁻¹ has also been observed in this complex.

In all these complexes the N-O stretching vibrations of the ligands shift towards lower frequencies by 10-20 cm⁻¹. νSb-O stretchings occur in the region 380-420 cm⁻¹¹⁵⁻¹⁷.

The PMR spectra of Ph₃Sb(ONCMe₂)₂ and Ph₃Sb(ONCEt₂)₂ show that resonances of protons on carbon atoms adjacent to the >C=N-O- group appear twice with equal intensity under normal conditions in CDCl₃. This may be expected, since the two radicals bound to this group are not equivalent because of the non-linearity of the >C=N-O group^{12,13,19}. The PMR spectra of the complexes, Ph₃Sb(ONCRR')₂, in which R and R' attached to the imino carbon atom are different, exhibit only one type of proton resonances at room temperature. This may suggest that at ambient temperature both oximate groups are equivalent in these complexes because of free rotation around Sb-O bonds. Following (Fig. 1.) confirmation may be assumed for such complexes.

These complexes resemble common alkoxides and carboxylates in some of the properties, the latter are all penta-coordinated with trigonal

Fig. 1

bipyramidal geometry in which more electronegative substituents occupy the apical positions with three phenyl groups at equatorial positions²⁰⁻²³. By analogy to these compounds, we may assume that these complexes may also have a trigonal bipyramidal geometry in which two oxygen atoms occupy apical positions (Fig. 1.)

Thermal Decomposition :

A different type of thermal decomposition has been observed in these complexes which is not observed hitherto in the triorganoantimony(V) compounds²⁴. When these complexes are heated under vacuum (0.1-1.0 mm) at about 170-230°, two products distilled out along with a black residue in distillation flask. The nature of the first product, a low boiling component obtained in a very poor yield, varies with the nature of the ligand. In case of $\text{Ph}_3\text{Sb}(\text{ONCMe}_2)_2$, nitrogen analysis, m.p. and i.r. spectra of low boiling component correspond to the free oxime. The second, high boiling component, obtained as a viscous mobile liquid contains some nitrogenous impurities from which it can be purified by redistillation. It has been identified as triphenylantimony. This mobile liquid can immediately be crystallized out (m.p. 47-48°) by adding a crystal of triphenylantimony. The IR spectra is similar in finger print region to that of triphenylantimony. PMR spectra exhibit only phenyl group resonances at 7.40-7.47 δ in CCl_4 .

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